

ASSESSING SOIL-SHAFT INTERACTION AT AN INSTRUMENTED BRIDGE IN CALIFORNIA IN TERMS OF EFFECTS OF SOIL-SHAFT NONLINEAR PROPERTIES IN VARIOUS EARTHQUAKE SCENARIOS

Reza Mohammadi, University of Nevada Reno, Nevada, USA, rmohammadi@unr.edu

Ramin Motamed, University of Nevada Reno, Nevada, USA, motamed@unr.edu

ABSTRACT

Finite element methods play a crucial role in analyzing dynamic responses within soil-foundation-structural systems during earthquakes. The validation of these models using seismic recordings is paramount for their application in the seismic design of foundations. This paper focuses on the refinement and validation of finite element models developed to study the response of drilled shafts at the Hayward-I580/238 bridge in California. The research methodology employs a two-step finite element modeling approach. In the initial phase, a free-field soil model of the site was developed in a two-dimensional model with OpenSees. Subsequently, a drilled shaft with an elastic section was modeled to investigate the response of the deep foundation to earthquake motions. However, acknowledging that these assumptions may not fully represent actual conditions, a three-dimensional free-field nonlinear soil column model of the bridge site was developed using OpenSees software in this study. Additionally, an inelastic section model for one of the bridge's drilled shafts was introduced to better capture the shaft's response under strong seismic forces. Given the relatively weak ground motions recorded by the accelerometers at the Hayward-I580/238 bridge, hypothetical earthquake scenarios were generated to depict the nonlinear response of the soil-shaft model. The available recorded motions were used to fit the target design spectrum at the Hayward-I580/238 bridge following AASHTO-2009. Subsequently, the shaft's reaction was analyzed under seismic forces, examining various parameters such as displacements and reaction forces. The results highlight the impact of the introduced modifications on the accuracy of the finite element models under both weak and strong earthquakes. In conclusion, the enhanced models not only contribute to monitoring drilled shaft behavior during seismic events but also establish a robust framework for future seismic designs of drilled shafts, showcasing the benefits of OpenSees in the seismic design of deep foundations.

Keywords: deep foundation, drilled shaft, OpenSees, soil-foundation interaction, seismic design

INTRODUCTION

Seismic events represent a significant risk to the integrity of infrastructure, particularly in regions susceptible to earthquakes. A detailed understanding of the dynamics between soil, ground movements, and structural responses is essential for the development of structures that are resilient to seismic forces (Reyes & Chopra, 2012; Imam et al., 2022; Mohammadzadeh et al., 2023). Historically, some of the most financially damaging earthquakes have occurred in California, significantly affecting its infrastructure, transportation networks, and critical facilities. Annually, the state suffers an estimated economic loss of around \$3.7 billion due to seismic activities, with more than 70% of these damages concentrated in major metropolitan areas such as Los Angeles, Long Beach, Santa Ana, as well as the San Francisco-Oakland-Fremont and Riverside-San Bernardino-Ontario regions (Faeli & Motamed, 2023). Over the past three decades, extensive research has been dedicated to analyzing the seismic behavior of bridges, leveraging empirical data (Gomez et al., 2013; Arici et al., 2003) and employing diverse assessment techniques to evaluate their seismic responses (Mosquera et al., 2012; Jazi, 2024). The significant role of ground dynamics and foundational support in influencing bridge reactions to earthquakes has prompted the integration of sensors within selected bridge shafts during their construction or renovation. This is aimed at examining the effects of soil-structure interactions. The valuable insights derived from seismic recordings significantly advance our understanding of the impact of soil-structure interactions on the seismic performance of bridge structures (Wang et al., 2022). Insights derived from seismic recordings

are invaluable for enhancing our understanding of how soil-structure interactions influence the stability of bridges during earthquakes (Shamsabadi et al., 2016). The seismic performance of a drilled shaft at the Hayward Bridge location was investigated using the OpenSees software. The behavior of both the free-field and the drilled shaft in response to recorded seismic events was analyzed. This analysis involved examining the free-field recordings from the Hayward Bridge as part of the BRACE2 project (Bridge Rapid Assessment Center for Extreme Events) and conducting numerical simulations (Mohammadi et al., 2023). However, the assumptions made for the numerical simulation may not fully represent actual conditions. Therefore, a three-dimensional free-field model of the bridge site was developed using OpenSees software in this study. Additionally, an inelastic section model for one of the bridge's drilled shafts was introduced to better capture the shaft's response to seismic forces. This study begins with a comprehensive description of the site and details of the instrumentation used to gather data at the research location. Subsequent sections introduce the seismic event scenarios considered for this study. The results from the two-dimensional free-field model and the three-dimensional model are then compared across various earthquake scenarios. This comparison is utilized to discuss the significance of considering bidirectional loading effects. Furthermore, an inelastic section model for one of the bridge's drilled shafts was introduced to better capture the shaft's response to seismic forces. The findings highlight the impact of the introduced modifications on the accuracy of the finite element models under both weak and strong earthquake conditions.

SITE DESCRIPTION AND INSTRUMENTATIONS

This study focuses on the Hayward - Hwy 580/238 interchange, which features a bridge composed of 14 spans of in-situ cast prestressed concrete box girders (refer to Fig. 1). Data collection was facilitated through instrumentation embedded within two boreholes, identified as the east and west geotechnical downhole arrays in Fig. 2, with a comprehensive description provided in Table 1. The site's foundation comprises rigid black clay and layers of hard to very hard slightly silty brown clay. These layers are underlain by a heavily altered and sheared green to greenish-gray gabbro, partially serpentinized, alongside similarly altered and sheared greenish-gray serpentine rock formations dating from the Jurassic to Cretaceous periods. Notably, the borehole near the eastern geotechnical array is characterized by approximately 1 m of stiff black clay overlying the altered sheared rock (see Table 2). In contrast, additional boreholes conducted along the bridge uncovered about 9 m (29.5 feet) of clayey and silty alluvial deposits. Historical data from Caltrans (1984) indicates that groundwater levels at the site range from 3 m to 8 m (10 feet to 26 feet) below the ground surface.

Fig. 1. Hayward - Hwy 580/238 Interchange featuring a 14-span cast-in-place pre-stressed concrete box girder bridge (Caltrans 2021).

Fig. 2. Location of West and East geotechnical downhole arrays (modified from Google Earth).

Table 1. Characteristics of the downhole instrumentation at Hayward Bridge

Geotechnical Downhole Array	Latitude (N)	Longitude (W)	Downhole Array depth (m)	Distance to Hayward bridge (m)	No. of Recorded Events	Sensor depths below ground surface (m)
East	37.6896	122.0962	91	30	3	0,9,30,91
West	37.6887	122.1074	91	625	12	0,5,9,18,37,91

Table 2. Sub-surface soil conditions at the geotechnical array sites

East Geotechnical Downhole Array		West Geotechnical Downhole Array	
Thickness (m)	Soil Description	Thickness (m)	Soil Description
1	Stiff black clay	6	Black to brown silty clay
24	Brown highly weathered sheared Gabbro	18	Olive green highly weathered sheared partially serpentinized Gabbro with calcite veinlets

METHODOLOGY

In this study, OpenSees software, which is extensively utilized for structural seismic analysis and modeling, was applied. The geotechnical borehole on the east side was selected for analysis due to its proximity to the Hayward-Highway 580/238 interchange, the primary focus of this research. Considering the relatively weak ground motions captured by the accelerometers at the Hayward-I580/238 bridge, hypothetical earthquake scenarios were generated to simulate the nonlinear behavior of the model. These scenarios facilitate the comparison of results from the two-dimensional free-field model and the three-dimensional model under various earthquake conditions. Such comparisons are crucial for evaluating the importance of bidirectional loading effects. Additionally, an inelastic section model for one of the bridge's

drilled shafts was implemented to enhance the accuracy of the shaft's response to seismic forces. Moreover, the effect of nonlinear modeling of the shaft section has been studied by comparing the responses of the elastic pile and inelastic pile under different seismic events.

Earthquake events

This investigation employed downhole arrays reaching a depth of 91 meters (298.5 feet) below the ground surface, outfitted with triaxial accelerometers at varying depths, as outlined in Table 1. These accelerometers were oriented at 90 degrees, 360 degrees, and vertically. Over the period from 2011 to 2022, a total of 15 seismic events were documented, with magnitudes ranging from Mw 3.4 to 6.0. Of these, three events were detected by the east geotechnical downhole array, and twelve by the west geotechnical downhole array. Details of the seismic excitations observed at the east geotechnical borehole are presented in Table 3. The acceleration data for these events were sourced as processed information from the Center for Engineering Strong Motion Data (CESMD).

Table 3. Characteristics of earthquake excitations captured at East geotechnical borehole (CESMD)

Downhole Array	No.	Earthquake Name	Earthquake date	Magnitude	PGA (g)	Epicentral distance (km)
	1	Berkeley	2018	4.4 M _w	0.017	23.2
East	2	San Lorenzo	2021	3.9 M _w	0.032	2.9
	3	San Ramon	2021	3.9 M _w	0.024	15.8

The OpenSees model has been validated against data from actual field instruments, and the behavior of the shaft has been studied under earthquake events captured at the east geotechnical array (refer to Mohammadi et al., 2023). However, as indicated in Table 3, all recorded earthquakes constitute weak excitations. Therefore, to evaluate the model's performance and compare the results under strong motion scenarios, four different scenarios have been defined, titled Berkley 2018, 0.52Target, Target, and 2.1Target. Additionally, the target design spectrum at the Hayward-I580/238 bridge has been established in accordance with AASHTO-2009. Taking into account the coordinates of the site and the site classification, the target design spectrum is depicted in Fig. 3. For Berkley 2018, the recorded excitations from the 2018 Mw 4.4 Berkeley earthquake were utilized, and the input motion of this event is used as a reference for defining the input motions in subsequent events. 0.52Target was defined to achieve a Peak Ground Acceleration (PGA) lower than the target design PGA at the surface. For Target, the input motion was defined to achieve a PGA of approximately 0.95 g, which matches the target design PGA at the ground surface. Finally, the input motions for 2.1Target were designed to include very strong motion in the model. Since the PGA at the ground surface exceeds the target design PGA, this event is designated only for evaluating the performance of the model under very strong motions, although such an event is less likely to occur at the site. The acceleration spectrum responses of the four scenarios in the N-S direction are shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 3. Target design spectrum of the Heyward bridge site following AASHTO 2009.

Fig. 4. Acceleration response spectra in N-S direction of soil column model, (a) Berkley 2018, (b) 0.52Target, (c) Target, and (d) 2.1Target.

Bi-directional shaking

The free-field model was constructed using data from a geotechnical borehole located in the eastern borehole of the site. The model features a 30-meter column segmented into 90 elements, each measuring 0.33 meters. The PressureIndependentMultiYield model was utilized to describe the soil's constitutive behavior, integrating a range of pertinent soil properties. The model's strength parameters were derived from the shear velocity (V_s) measurements of the soil layers, accounting for the soil's elastoplastic behavior and resulting in hysteretic damping (refer to Mohammadi et al., 2023). To implement the Lysmer-Kuhlemeyer (1969) dashpot, a viscous uniaxial material was applied, and a zeroLength element was employed to link the two designated dashpot nodes. In the unidirectional loading model (1-D), the

soil was represented using four-node quad elements in a plane strain formulation. Conversely, in the bidirectional loading model (2-D), the soil column was modeled using stdBrick elements. The input motions from the mentioned earthquake events were applied to the models, and the site responses of the models were analyzed and compared. Fig. 6 illustrates the acceleration responses of the 1-D and 2-D models at the ground surface in the N-S direction. As depicted in Fig. 6, the acceleration spectrum responses of the 1-D and 2-D models are aligned for Berkley 2018. Nonetheless, a subtle discrepancy is evident in the results for 0.52Target. Moreover, for Target and 2.1Target, the differences in the acceleration spectrum responses become significantly more pronounced. Figure 7(a) depicts the maximum shear strain of the model at various depths for different seismic events. As illustrated in Figure 7(a), the maximum shear strains for Berkley 2018 remain within the linear range, indicating minimal nonlinearity in the soil's response. In contrast, the nonlinear behavior of the soil model for 0.52Target is marginally evident. However, for Target and 2.1Target, the soil exhibits significant nonlinear behavior.

Fig. 6. Acceleration response spectra in N-S direction of free-field soil column model, (a) Berkley 2018, (b) 0.52Target, (c) Target, and (d) 2.1Target.

In order to have better insight into the difference in the result of 1-D and 2-D free-field modeling, an average bias is defined (Boushehri et al. 2022) as the difference between the 1-D and 2-D spectral acceleration (in logarithmic units).

$$R_d(ave) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \log(s_i^{1D}) - \log(s_i^{2D})}{n} \quad [1]$$

where $R_d(ave)$ is the average residual, S_i^{1D} and S_i^{2D} denote the acceleration spectrum responses of the 1-D and 2-D models at the surface for each period, respectively. Fig. 7(b) shows the values of $R_d(ave)$ against the maximum shear strain for each event.

Fig. 7. Maximum shear strain in N-S direction in free-field soil column model, (a) against depth, (b) against average residual.

Pile section

In subsequent sections of the paper, a model of the drilled shaft is constructed, and the acceleration responses derived from the free-field model for different seismic events are integrated. The shaft's cross-section comprises a 2.29 m (90 inches) diameter, reinforced with 84 number #14 bars. Nodes for the shaft are established with three dimensions and six degrees of freedom, forming a 12-meter-tall column segmented into 36 elements, each 0.33 meters in size. The interaction between the soil and the shaft is modeled using an array of springs arranged in two distinct directions, with zero-length elements utilized to connect the designated spring nodes. The constitutive behavior of these springs is specified such that the lateral springs (in the N-S and W-E directions) function as p-y springs. Given that the p-y curves available in OpenSees primarily pertain to sandy soil, a hysteretic constitutive model is adapted to represent the p-y curve for the clay and weak rock layers present at the site. Key parameters for the hysteretic model in clay and weak rock are determined based on p-y curves obtained, following the methodology proposed by Rees et al. The shaft is initially modeled to display elastic behavior using an elastic section object in conjunction with a displacement-based beam element (dispBeamColumn). In one scenario, this setup is retained to reflect the shaft's purely elastic response. In another scenario, to accurately capture the shaft's response during seismic events, the inelastic behavior of the shaft's section is considered. Consequently, a fiber section is selected for detailed modeling (Matinrad, 2023). Concrete02 and steel02 materials are employed for the concrete and reinforcing bars, respectively. When modeling the section as an inelastic fiber section, employing a force-based beam-column element is advantageous over the displacement-based element (dispBeamColumn), as the former accounts for nonlinear curvature distribution along the element's length, unlike the linear curvature assumption inherent in the displacement-based formulation.

In order to have better insight into the difference between the response of the shaft with the elastic section and the shaft modeled with the inelastic section, the residual value (R_s) is defined.

$$R_s = \log(S^{elastic}) - \log(S^{inelastic}) \quad [2]$$

where R_s is the residual, $S^{elastic}$ and $S^{inelastic}$ denote the acceleration spectrum responses of the elastic shaft and the inelastic shaft at the surface for each period, respectively.

Figure 8 illustrates the values of R_s for various seismic events. As demonstrated in the figure, R_s values decrease as the seismic events intensify. For Berkley 2018, the R_s value is nearly zero, indicating that incorporating the inelastic section into the pile did not alter the shaft's response for this event. However, in 2.1Target, the introduction of the inelastic section in the model resulted in a significant modification of the shaft's response. Figure 9 displays the stress-strain relationship of the confined concrete at depths of 3m and 6m for specified events. As depicted, during Berkley 2018, the concrete exhibits elastic behavior, which correlates with the R_s the values being close to zero. For 0.52Target, the concrete demonstrates a slight inelastic behavior. However, in Target and 2.1Target, the concrete behavior is distinctly nonlinear.

Fig. 8. Residual values of acceleration response spectrum of the shaft at the ground surface at each period for different scenarios in the N-S direction.

Fig. 9. Stress-strain of the concrete component of the shaft, (a) Berkley 2018, (b) 0.52Target, (c) Target, and (d) 2.1Target.

DISCUSSION

In the initial discussions of this study, it is important to note that the recorded earthquake events at the site were predominantly weak. Consequently, to thoroughly evaluate the performance of the OpenSees model, it was necessary to define several strong hypothetical earthquake scenarios. These events were designed to represent Peak Ground Acceleration (PGA) values that are below, above, and equal to the target design PGA at the surface. However, for generating earthquake scenarios at a site, more complex and detailed approaches could be utilized, which would yield more precise outcomes. One of the primary objectives of this research is to demonstrate that both the free-field and the shaft-soil models are capable of accurately simulating the behavior of soil and shaft under strong motions as well, a capability that has been successfully validated in this study. When comparing the results of the free-field model for two-dimensional (2-D) and one-dimensional (1-D) loading, it is observed that for the weak motions, particularly considering the stiff site conditions at the Hayward Bridge, there is no significant difference in the results. However, under strong motion, the soil exhibits nonlinear behavior, leading to noticeable differences between the 1-D and 2-D results. Figure 7(b), which illustrates the maximum strain values for each event, shows that the fit curve tends to flatten upon reaching the nonlinearity threshold (maximum shear strain = 0.1%). This suggests that the average residual value, $R_d(ave)$, does not undergo significant changes once the soil transitions into the nonlinear zone. However, substantiating this claim requires further data collection and detailed analysis. Thus, it presents an excellent opportunity for future research to explore this phenomenon more comprehensively. Further comparisons of the shaft's response, considering both the elastic and inelastic sections for modeling, reveal that for weak ground motions, where the shaft still behaves elastically, there are no discernible differences in results. However, for strong ground motions, which induce nonlinear behavior in the shaft section, the outcomes are significantly different. Employing an elastic section model, as opposed to an inelastic one, tends to overestimate the results and lacks precision.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

This research investigated the seismic behavior of drilled shafts at the Hayward-I580/238 interchange through the application of finite element models. Employing OpenSees software, the study initially developed a two-dimensional free-field soil model, progressing to a more sophisticated three-dimensional model to account for the effect of bi-directional loadings. An inelastic section model of the drilled shaft was incorporated to enhance the accuracy of the seismic response simulation under various earthquake scenarios. This approach enabled the exploration of the dynamic interactions between the soil and structural elements under both weak and strong seismic excitations, using hypothetical earthquake scenarios to supplement the recorded motions at the site. The findings emphasize the significance of the modifications made to the finite element models, demonstrating their improved accuracy in simulating seismic responses under both weak and strong earthquake conditions. Ultimately, the refined models not only help in tracking the behavior of drilled shafts during seismic activities but also lay a strong foundation for the future design of such structures. This underscores the utility of OpenSees software in enhancing the seismic design of deep foundations.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors express their gratitude to the Pacific Earthquake Engineering Research Center (PEER) for their support and valuable recommendations from Professor Khalid Mosalam, who serves as the Director of PEER at UC Berkeley. The perspectives, discoveries, and deductions presented in this publication are exclusively those of the authors and might not coincide with the opinions of the supporting organization, PEER.

REFERENCES

- Arici, Y., & Mosalam, K. M., 2003. System identification of instrumented bridge systems. *Earthquake engineering & structural dynamics*, 32(7), 999-1020.
- Caltrans., 1984. Foundation investigation report, Hayward-I580/238 bridge, 33-0214L.
- Caltrans Geotechnical manual, soil correlations., 2021. Caltrans Division of Engineering Services, Geotechnical Services.
- Center for Engineering Strong Motion Data., 2023. CESMD: Center for Engineering Strong Motion Data, <https://www.strongmotioncenter.org/>
- Faeli, Z., & Motamed, R. Hayward Bridge Geotechnical Array Soil Dynamic Properties. In *Geo-Congress 2023* (pp. 257-267).
- Imam, S.R., Mohammadi, R. and Ghafarian, D., Analysis of soil subsidence due to change in groundwater level in unsaturated soils.
- Exploring the Importance of Natural Convection Mechanism on Heat Transfer Response of Soil Medium in the Presence of an Unconfined Groundwater Flow
- Lysmer, J., & Kuhlemeyer, R. L., 1969. Finite dynamic model for infinite media. *Journal of the Engineering Mechanics Division*, 95(4), 859-877.
- Matinrad, P., & Petrone, F. (2023). ASCE/SEI 7-compliant site-specific evaluation of the seismic demand posed to reinforced concrete buildings with real and simulated ground motions. *Earthquake Engineering & Structural Dynamics*, 52(15), 4987-5009.
- Mohammadzadeh, A., Najafian Jazi, F., Ghasemi-Fare, O., & Sun, Z. Analyzing the Feasibility of Using Shallow Geothermal Energy to Prohibit Pavement Thermal Cracking: Field Testing. In *Geo-Congress 2023* (pp. 603-611).
- Mohammadi, R. Motamed, R., and Faeli, Z. (2023) "Numerical Modeling of Soil-Shaft Interaction Validated Using the Instrumented Hayward Bridge in California" *DFI 48th Annual Conference on Deep Foundations*, October 31-November 3 2023, Seattle, WA, pp. 620-630.
- Mosquera, V., Smyth, A. W., & Betti, R., 2012. Rapid evaluation and damage assessment of instrumented highway bridges. *Earthquake Engineering & Structural Dynamics*, 41(4), 755-774.
- Reese, L., and Nyman, K., 1978. Field load tests of instrumented drilled shafts at Islamorada, Florida. Report to the Girdler Foundation and Exploration Corporation, Clearwater, FL, February.
- Reyes, J. C., & Chopra, A. K., 2012. Modal pushover-based scaling of two components of ground motion records for nonlinear RHA of structures. *Earthquake Spectra*, 28(3), 1243-1267.
- Shamsabadi, A., Abazarsa, F., Ghahari, S. F., Nigbor, R., & Taciroglu, E., 2016. Bridge instrumentation: needs, options, and consequences. In *Developments in international bridge engineering: Selected papers from Istanbul Bridge Conference 2014* (pp. 199-210). Springer International Publishing.
- Wang, N., Elgamal, A., & Lu, J., 2022. Seismic response of the Eureka Channel Bridge-Foundation system. *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering*, 152, 107015.